

SINGLE FIBRE AND HYBRID COMPOSITES WITH ALIGNED DISCONTINUOUS FIBRES IN POLYMER MATRIX

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SUMMARY

By using special processes, composites with aligned discontinuous fibres can be produced, which show properties similar to comparable composites with continuous fibres. MBB has developed the VTF-alignment-process (vacuum-drum-filter) in the past years.

It is a simple process based on the hydrodynamic principle. The short fibres are aligned by laminar streams and deposited on the surface of a vacuum drum filter. After washing and impregnating the fibre felts, composites can be made by hot pressing. The two essential advantages of these composites are the possibilities to manufacture

- parts with complex shapes and
- hybrids by mixing the elementary fibres in any proportions.

MBB has tested the mechanical and processing properties of these composites, especially carbon and glass fibres in epoxy resins.

INTRODUCTION

For several years discontinuous glass fibres have been used with different processes to reinforce resins. The fundamental characteristics of these materials is the random arrangement of the fibres. This increases the modulus of the resin-fibre composite, but has little effect on the strength properties. To get composites with optimal properties in stiffness and strength a perfect parallel alignment of the fibres is necessary.

With continuous fibres such composites are made, for example, by filament winding.

The development of practical alignment processes for short fibres was highly stimulated by the availability of high strength whiskers which were considered to be an ideal reinforcement for metals and polymers. Because of high cost and technical problems, whiskers have never been used to any large extent. The alignment processes, however, were successfully used for glass and carbon fibres and it could be shown that the corresponding short fibre composite possesses many attractive advantages.

ALIGNING PROCESS

The literature describes various processes for aligning discontinuous fibres by electrical, magnetic and hydrodynamic means.

For practical applications, only one system, hydrodynamic alignment, especially in glycerine has found its way into pilot-plant scale operation. Two variants are available:

- the PERME process (1)
- the MBB-VTF system, which will be described following.
It is based on the hydrodynamic principle as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: MBB-VTF process

In the mixing tank the fibres are suspended in a liquid carrier by using a mechanical impeller. From there, the suspension flows through a channel onto a rotating vacuum drum filter.

During the flow in the specially designed channel and during the transfer from the channel onto the drum, the fibres become perfectly aligned parallel to each other and are deposited on the drum in the direction of rotation. The liquid carrier is removed by suction and the aligned fibres are kept on the drum surface, which has previously been covered with a filter cloth. The quantity of the suspension flowing onto the drum is adjusted to the speed of the rotating drum in a way that the liquid can be sucked off almost immediately. The slope of the channel and the transfer geometry to the drum are optimised in order to give a laminar and steady flow over the whole width of the drum. The carrier medium is collected in a tank for re-use.

The essential parameters for producing fibre felts are:

- fibre length
- fibre concentration in the liquid carrier
- rotating speed of the drum
- suction speed of the liquid carrier.

The thickness of the sheets produced depends on the quantity of suspension which is fed to the drum. Once the required thickness is reached, the glycerine flow is stopped.

Complete removal of the carrier medium is achieved by water spray washing on the vacuum drum filter. The washing water is collected in a second tank. Now the wet fibre sheet is taken from the drum and dried. After impregnating with resin solution and evaporating the solvent, prepregs are ready for further processing.

Compression moulding is used as the standard manufacturing procedure. It was found that the pressure required depends strongly on the desired fibre content and on the degree of alignment. (Lack of parallel alignment leads to "crossing" of fibres and fragmentation at higher pressures.) Perfectly aligned fibre felts permit

achievement of 50% fibre volumes at pressures below 10 bars.

Because of these relatively low pressures both hot presses and autoclaves can be used.

THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Besides the degree of alignment and the fibre content, the ratio of fibre length to fibre diameter is important for the reinforcing effect. Theoretical considerations have shown that with discontinuous fibres the properties of corresponding continuous fibre composites can almost be reached under the following ideal conditions:

- adequate length-to-diameter ratio (about 1000:1)
- 100% alignment
- ideal elastoplastic properties of the resin (2) (3).

Figures 2 and 3 show the tensile strength and modulus of different composites as a function of the fibre length to diameter ratio.

Figure 2: Theoretical tensile strength

Figure 3: Theoretical tensile modulus

It is obvious that ideal conditions cannot be found in technical processes. Fibre alignment, while being extremely good, is not 100% perfect and the fibre length is limited by technological considerations. For the MBB-VTF process, a fibre length of 2-4 mm was found to offer the best compromise, which means length-to-diameter ratios of 200-400. With increasing fibre length a deterioration of the grade of alignment is observed due to interaction between the fibres during the flow in the alignment channel.

PROPERTIES OF UNIDIRECTIONAL DISCONTINUOUS FIBRE COMPOSITES

MBB has tested the processing properties of various reinforcement fibres and the mechanical properties of the resulting composites. Carbon and glass fibres in epoxy resin were examined in detail. Table 1 contains the essential results achieved with unidirectional composites. The properties depend on the type of fibre and resin. The reported values are based on the carbon fibres of Courtaulds (S-types without finish), on E-glass of Gevetex and on epoxy resins from Ciba and Shell. Further types of fibres like asbestos and aramide fibres were evaluated, but could not be aligned satisfactorily because of the irregular shapes. Fatigue tests and the examination of crossplied composites are being performed at present.

	HT/EP	HM/EP	A/EP	Glass/EP
Flexural strength (kN/mm ²)	1,2-1,4	0,8-0,9	1,0-1,2	0,7-0,8
Flexural modulus (kN/mm ²)	100-110	130-150	80-90	30-40
Tensile strength (kN/mm ²)	1,1-1,3	-	-	-
Tensile modulus (kN/mm ²)	100-110	-	-	-
Int. shear strength (N/mm ²)	70-90	40-50	65-75	60-70
Impact strength (mJ/mm ²)	60	28	-	150
Density (g/cm ³)	1,5	1,6	1,5	1,9

Table 1: Properties of unidirectional discontinuous fibre composites
Fibre content 50-55 Vol. %

HYBRID COMPOSITES

In this presentation hybrid composites are defined as a resin reinforced simultaneously with two types of fibres, which are different in their properties.

There are three possibilities of hybrid composites:

- 1 Dimensional (1D). Composite layers of different composition alternating with each other. Usually this is achieved by stacking different prepregs, e.g. glass and carbon.

A hybrid effect is seen only in z-direction (1D). This type of hybrid can be produced both with continuous and discontinuous fibres. (Figure 4)

- 2 Dimensional (2D). This material consists of a mixture of fibres, where each layer contains both types of fibres side by side. The hybrid-effect is seen in the z- and x-directions(2D). These composites can be produced advantageously with continuous fibres. (Figure 5)

- 3 Dimensional composites (3D). In this case, fibre properties alternate also in the fibre direction (y-axis). Obviously such a perfect hybrid can only be obtained by a mixture of discontinuous fibres. (Figure 6)

An additional feature should be considered. Conventional glass or carbon fibres consist of rovings with hundreds and thousands of elementary fibres. By contrast, the VTF processes desintegrate the rovings into the elementary fibres. The resulting hybrid, therefore, is on a much finer scale.

Figure 4: Mixture of layers (1D)

Figure 5: Mixture of fibres (2D)

Figure 6: Mixture of discontinuous fibres (3D)

Niki and Tagiri have provided a theoretical basis for the computation of the mechanical properties of hybrids consisting of alternating layers (1D) with continuous fibres. It appears that tensile properties can be predicted from the values of the constituent fibres (rule of mixture).

Our investigations have shown that this is true, also, for discontinuous hybrids. By way of contrast, discrepancies have been found in flexural testing, where the mechanical properties of 1D composites depend strongly on the stacking sequence of the individual layers and on the outmost (compression or tensions) layers.

The bulk of the present program concerns 1D and 3D glass/carbon composites (some preliminary tests were performed on Kevlar and boron hybrids).

The following points were investigated:

- Feasibility of manufacturing hybrids with large variations of fibre ratios
- Moulding characteristics
- Differences between 1D and 3D systems
- Mechanical properties.

Glass/carbon ratios of 9:1, 8:2, 2:1, 1:1, 1:2, 2:8 and 1:9 were tested in detail. All mixtures, even the 9:1 materials, could be prepared without any problems and with a relatively homogenous distribution of the two components.

Typical examples are shown in Figures 7 and 8 which illustrate glass/carbon ratios of 2:8 and 8:2, respectively. (Carbon fibres are the small clear circles.) It can be seen from these pictures that an excellent statistical distribution can be obtained. The circular shapes of the fibre cross-sections are an indication of the high degree of parallel alignment.

Figure 7: Carbon/glass fibres 8:2

Figure 8: Carbon/glass fibre 2:8

Several test articles using glass/carbon hybrids were manufactured and no difficulties were encountered. Examples will be shown later.

Evaluation of the mechanical data yields interesting results. While 1D and 3D composites show approximately the same values for elastic modulus and for impact strength, the 3D material is largely superior (up to 20%) in flexural strength, tensile strength and interlaminar shear strength.

It is assumed that this is due to differences in the levels of internal stresses in both materials. Glass and carbon have different coefficients of thermal expansion. In hybrids, cooling from the curing temperature will therefore create a system of tension and compression stresses. When solid layers of each fibre system are stacked as preregs over each other, stress relaxation is difficult,

stress fields are smaller and relaxation is made easier in the 3D composites. Because of the superior properties of the 3D material, tests of the 1D ("prepreg by prepreg") systems have been discontinued.

3D hybrids with discontinuous fibres offer an attractive way for hybridization. This is underscored by the results obtained at PERME with HT/HM carbon fibre hybrids.

It was found that 3D glass/carbon hybrids generally exhibit properties which would be expected from the law of mixtures without, however, the drop in strength postulated by some theories at low percentages of a second fibre.

Figure 9 and Figure 10 show typical data for flexural modulus and impact strength.

Figure 9: Flexural modulus

Figure 10: Impact strength

(The base line data for the single fibre materials have been improved in the meantime.) An interesting hybridization effect is observed for additions of approximately 10% glass to the carbon fibres: While impact strength increases considerably over the pure carbon, the elastic values remain approximately constant. While the impact values of hybrids appear to vary with the type and make of the fibre, the retention of high modulus values up to about 20% glass has been reconfirmed by repeated testing. This feature appears also interesting for applications were cost is of overriding importance.

APPLICATIONS

Composites with discontinuous fibres can never replace to a large extent the conventional continuous fibre materials. However, they offer some intriguing advantages for specific applications.

- Since the discontinuous fibres can slide relative to each other, they exhibit unusually good draping properties and permit the moulding of complex shapes.
- The improved energy absorption characteristics of 3D glass/carbon hybrids are of advantage for components where impact resistance is required.
- Because both continuous fibres and cloth can be transformed into discontinuous fibres, this technology may offer an economic way for the recycling of cut-offs and left-over material.

Typical areas for the use of discontinuous fibre composites include:

- Moulded components with complex shapes which require strong deformation of the prepregs or moulding, e.g. ogival shapes, covers, flaps, antennas.
- Components with tight radii in different directions and with varying thickness.
- Compact parts with heavy cross-sections.
- External parts of missiles and aircraft, subject to local impact during handling and service.
- Glass/carbon hybrid components permitting a close trade-off between cost and performance.

Figure 11 shows the cover of a missile which was manufactured in an autoclave at a pressure below 10 bars. Discontinuous fibres facilitate moulding of this ogive. The sine wave illustrated in Figure 12 is built up mainly from $\pm 45^\circ$ cross-plyies. Web and flange are manufactured together in one step, the tight radius between the two showing the excellent draping properties of the material.

Figure 13 is a cross-section through the window frame of a transport aircraft molded from a unidirectional ring of aligned discontinuous fibres. This ring is not built up from individual prepregs, but made from one thick layer of discontinuous fibres.

Figure 14 again shows an example for an extremely tight radius realised in the wing-fuselage connection of a missile airframe. The integral construction of these components results in considerable weight savings due to the lack of attachments and fasteners.

Figure 11: Cover for missiles

Figure 12: Sine wave

Figure 13: Window frame for aeroplanes

Figure 14: Interpal part for missiles

CONCLUSIONS

Discontinuous fibre composites offer some basic differences as compared to conventional materials. Generally speaking, processing and handling characteristics are considerably improved, some of the mechanical properties are decreased. Hybridization is made much easier and offers some distinct advantages. The growing use of carbon fibres will strongly increase the supply of left-over or cutouts, both fibres and prepregs. The short fibre technology will probably be able to recycle some of this material. This will increase its cost-savings potential.

The VTF process for making discontinuous fibre prepreg has been licensed to a manufacturing company and the material is now available on the open market.

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Figure 15: Processing and material properties of aligned discontinuous fibres

